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Saigas are returning to the Russian Trans-Volga region

Before the break-up of the USSR, the border areas of the present-day Russian Trans-Volga region were part of the continuous range of the Volga-Ural saiga population. This includes the northern part of the Lower Trans-Volga area, where saigas summer and calve, as well as the Baskunchak lake area where saigas spend the winter. In the second half of the 1990s, saiga numbers catastrophically declined and their range shrank significantly.

In the last decade, the Volga-Ural population in Western Kazakhstan has been steadily growing; according to official data the population has increased twentyfold in this period, so it is now more than double the historical maximum size (of about 300,000 individuals; *Milner-Gulland et al. 2001*), reaching $810,000 \pm 150,000$ individuals by spring 2022. During the population's low point, only single individuals were found on Russian territory, but starting from 2015–2018 the species range began to expand again eastwards and northwards.

For much of the year saigas remain in Kazakhstan near the border with the Saratov, Volgograd and Astrakhan provinces of the Russian Federation. However, in 2018–2021, when the

region was impacted by strong droughts, saigas visited the Russian Lower Trans-Volga area in exceptionally large numbers and remained there for at least one month. According to experts, in June and July 2020, there were 45,000–50,000 individuals in this area.

Data on the numbers and distribution of saigas in the Russian Trans-Volga region are based mainly on interviews. The only attempt to estimate the population size was made by the authors of this article in late August 2021, when 1,142 animals were recorded during a survey on a 435-km transect. Extrapolation to the territory occupied by saigas at that time (4,271 km²) produced a population estimate of 28,000–33,000 individuals; taking into

account areas that were not surveyed, it could be up to 38,000 individuals. In our opinion, the number of saigas in the spring could be 1.5–2 times higher.

Every year, about 80% of this area's saiga population stays in the northern part of the region, north of Lake Elton, within four municipal districts in the south-east of Saratov province (especially Alexandrovo-Gaysky and Novouzensky) and two districts in the north-east of Volgograd province (particularly Pallasovsky District). They usually begin to enter the area in large numbers in April, with a peak in May and June. For several years, saigas have been calving annually here, and in some places large numbers of calving antelopes were recorded in 2020–2022. Presumably, the Russian territory is not only the periphery of a temporary summer habitat for the Volga-Ural saiga population, but also an important breeding ground. Towards the autumn activity drops and remains low throughout the winter.

In the southern half of the Trans-Volga region (southern half of Pallasovsky District, Akhtubinsky and Kharabalinsky Districts of Astrakhan province), saigas are present in significantly smaller numbers, which decrease rapidly towards the south.

Saigas grazing on a harvested grain field near the village of Serogodsky, Pallasovsky District of Volgograd province. September 2021. Photo by Ilya Smelyansky

Saiga movements into the Trans-Volga region do not represent long-distance directional migration, but are relatively short-distance movements within areas of seasonal concentration, with a tendency to shift to the territory of the previously lost part of their historical range. They rarely move further than 25–30 km from the border with Kazakhstan and concentrate near areas of mass border crossings (Fig. 1). In the spring and summer of 2020–2022, females and juveniles predominated, with adult males making up less than 15% of the animals observed. Throughout the winter and until early April, adult males accounted

for up to half of the population, and in some places even more.

There is a small relatively sedentary group of saigas (up to 4,000 individuals as of September 2021) in an area near Lake Bulukhta that is little used by humans. All other saiga herds in the Russian Trans-Volga region are transboundary and for them it is critically important to be able to cross the state border. In Saratov province, most of the border is free of artificial barriers, but in some places saigas have to cross rivers (the Small and Large Uzen, Dura and Gorkaya). To the south, a barbed wire fence has been installed along

almost all the border to prevent livestock from crossing it. Saigas pass across the border by breaking through the wire or finding gaps in the fence, which is not an insurmountable obstacle, but may cause injuries and sometimes even kill the animals. In 2021, several openings were made in the barrier in Astrakhan province specifically for saigas.

The main anthropogenic threats that affect most of the saigas, covering the entire northern half of the region, are poaching and conflicts with farmers and pastoralists. Poaching is not at a commercial scale, and is estimated

Fig. 1. Distribution of the Volga-Ural saiga population in the regions adjacent to the Lower Trans-Volga region in Russia and Kazakhstan

not to exceed 1% of the population. As far as we know, conflicts with agriculturalists have not so far led to direct killing of saigas, but they have resulted in numerous cases of deliberate disturbance, including before and during calving, which increases mortality, at least among newborns. The causes of conflicts are damage to crops and hayfields (trampling, to a lesser extent grazing) and competition between saigas and livestock for watering holes.

In the absence of organised poaching, the safety of saiga in the Russian Trans-Volga region depends on the attitude of the local population, which differs in the southern and northern parts of the region. In the south, there are no crops or valuable hayfields, so most people there have a positive attitude to saigas, not generally expecting trouble from them and showing willingness to help if necessary. People in the north regard saigas as a threat to agriculture, and a negative attitude prevails there; the presence of saigas is treated as a natural disaster that should be eliminated.

However, there are not many reliably established observations or quantitative estimates of damage to crops and hayfields. In 2020, reports of damage by saigas came from 10–15 rural settlements in six municipal districts of two provinces. Damage to several dozen farms and small agricultural companies was officially confirmed. The total cost of damage to 13 farms in two districts was estimated at more than 13 million roubles (over \$200,000).

The severe conflicts of 2019–2020 (for example, in Novouzensky District of Saratov province and Pallasovsky

District of Volgograd province) were significantly aggravated by drought. The farmers' demands to get rid of saigas and receive compensation for losses were then discussed at the level of the provincial government. In spring 2022, when saigas crossed the border in similar numbers, but in favourable weather conditions, the farmers were much less concerned.

There is also the issue of the potential risk of the transmission of dangerous infectious and parasitic diseases across the border from saigas to livestock. There are no reliably established reports of such transmission in the region, but concerns are widespread across all the three provinces, both among livestock breeders and agriculture specialists and in various administrative organisations.

About 14% of the areas where saigas concentrate in the Trans-Volga region are within five areas with different levels of protection (a state nature reserve, two natural parks and two regional reserves). Another 17% of the territory is minimally protected as a border zone. In total, almost a third of the area used by saigas is under some kind of formal protection. In some areas where saigas concentrate, the proportion protected is significantly higher (almost 90% around Lake Baskunchak) or lower (10% in the Kharabali area and 19% in the interfluvium between the Dura and Altata).

However, in most regional protected areas the regime and organisation of protection do not meet the goals of saiga conservation and do not fully protect the animals. The protection of saigas outside federal protected areas is the responsibility of the regions' environmental and law enforcement

services. Unfortunately, they do not have enough resources (only 6–7 rangers operate in 8 municipal districts, which means on average one ranger has to control a territory of at least 650,000 hectares). Provincial environmental authorities have groups tasked with combatting poaching, but there are only 1–2 groups in each province and they cannot pay much attention to saiga protection. Border protection authorities make a great contribution to the cause, detecting and preventing at least 70% of all known cases of poaching in the region.

Taking into account current trends, we can expect more saigas from the Volga-Ural population to move into the Russian Trans-Volga region. In order to conserve these animals, it is necessary to establish two new protected areas, implement conflict mitigation measures, organise regular monitoring of the animals' numbers and distribution and ensure ongoing interaction with Kazakh colleagues.

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